

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit analysis

Tool / Technology: Drone (quadruple drone)

Analysis prepared by (country): Norway

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Norway

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 120 ha (10 ha arable land and fenced pasture. Abundant rangeland grazing area for summer grazing.)

Species: Sheep / Goat

Number of animals: 80 ewes

Breed: Norwegian white sheep

Number of staff: 1

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N° 101000471.

Costs

• **Capital costs (e.g. large items):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

• **Individual costs (e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

• **Leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

• **Infrastructure requirements:**

Decrease Increase No change

• **Power source requirements:**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

• **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology: _____%**

• **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

• **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

• **Licences or permits required? Yes / No**

○ If yes, cost:

€1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

• **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range: Up to an hour Half day Full day More

• **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

• **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription: Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

• **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.)
- Management decisions for animal groupings
- Better individual animal management
- Improved medicine use
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.)
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.)
- Increased information on production system
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location)

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s)
- Improved welfare of the animals(s)
- Additional information on animal behaviour
- Information on water intake / water availability
- Information on food intake / food availability

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices
- Ease of data transfer to other software
- Easy to use once installed

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)

- Helps to attract new entrants in to the small ruminant industries

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Surveillance of animals on unfenced rangeland pastures is a concern and the gathering of sheep from these areas before winter is time consuming. In addition to saving work hours, as the drone can search a larger area, also health and safety can be improved. Using the drone to move sheep from steep hills and rocky landscape is a health and safety issue for people.

May be the tool that will keep sheep farmers into sheep farming, as well as allowing recruitment of young farmers.

Overall summary:

- **Recommend this tool/technology for this type of benchmark farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

The use of the drone can be restricted by weather conditions.

